

Abstract

Bioelectrical Changes in *Ren Mai* and *Du Mai* Acupoints During *Qigong*: A Quantitative Study of the 'White Ball' Exercise.

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Abstract

Background: *Qigong* is a cornerstone therapeutic modality of Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), integrating deliberate, fluid movements and specific postures with regulated breathing and a meditative state of 'awareness'. According to TCM theory, *Qigong* facilitates the 'circulation of *Qi*'—specifically the ascent of *Yang Qi* and the descent of *Yin Qi*—to establish systemic equilibrium. In Western physiological terms, this process is broadly analogous to achieving vegetative homeostasis and a state of emotional regulation.

Objective: Previous research into the functional movement of *Qi* has frequently relied on skin electrical resistance measurements. However, these methodologies have often faced challenges regarding validation, repeatability, and interpretation. This study aimed to address these limitations by measuring changes in skin electrical potential between specific points within the same meridian system during active practice.

Methods: The study assessed fluctuations in skin electrical potential at key acupoints along the *Ren Mai* (Conception Vessel) and *Du Mai* (Governing Vessel) conduits, alongside other points of interest. Measurements were recorded while participants performed a specific *Qigong* exercise known as the 'White Ball'.

Results: Significant changes in skin electrical potential were observed at several key points. Along the *Du Mai* conduit, notable shifts occurred at *Mingmén* (GV 4), *Shèndào* (GV 11), and *Bǎihuì* (GV 20). Along the *Ren Mai* conduit, significant activity was recorded at *Huìyīn* (CV 1), *Qìhǎi* (CV 6), *Zhōngwǎn* (CV 12), and *Tánzhōng* (CV 17).

Conclusions: These findings align with traditional TCM theoretical frameworks regarding energy flow. Furthermore, they provide a measurable physiological basis for the vegetative changes associated with the 'circulation of *Qi*', offering a potential bridge between traditional practice and bioelectrical monitoring.

Keywords: Electrical Potential; Heidelberg Model of TCM; *Qigong*; Vegetative Biofeedback; *Qi*.

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